

Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of Biacetyl Thiosemicarbazone and Biacetyl-(4-Phenyl)-Thiosemicarbazone

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Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes of the multidentate ligands biacetyl thiosemicarbazone and biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemicarbazone (LH_2 and L_1H_2) in the enol form have been synthesised. The complexes have the general formula ML_nH_2O and $ML_1_nH_2O$ [$M = Cu(II), Ni(II)$ and $Co(II)$ and $n = 0-2$]. A number of mixed-ligand complexes have also been synthesised. These were of the type $ML(B)_2$ and $ML_1(B)_2$ (where $B = py, 2-pic, 3-pic$ and $4-pic$). These complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, magnetic moment values, visible and infra-red spectra. The bonding sites and the geometry of the ligand environment around the metal ion have been discussed in the light of the physicochemical data obtained.

THE coordination chemistry of the thiosemicarbazones have assumed new importance because of the recent observations about the antibacterial and antitumour activities of some thiosemicarbazones and a few of their metal complexes¹⁻⁶. After making a thorough search of the relevant literature we decided to undertake a systematic study of the ligational behaviour of some thiosemicarbazones and substituted thiosemicarbazones of α, α' -diketones towards some transition metal ions present in the living systems. The ligands chosen for this purpose are biacetyl thiosemicarbazone and biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemicarbazone.

Both the ligands (LH_2 and L_1H_2) can exist in the keto : and the enol-forms and can act as neutral tetradentate or as biprotic tetradentate chelating ligands.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands : An alcoholic solution of thiosemicarbazide was prepared by refluxing 0.2 mole of it with 400-450 ml ethanol. To it 0.1 mole of biacetyl was added and the resulting solution was refluxed for about 4 hrs. Some of the alcohol was then distilled off until the yellowish, crystalline thiosemicarbazone began to separate. It was then cooled in a refrigerator, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused $CaCl_2$. (m.p. 235°, Requires C 31.03%, H 5.17%, N 36.21% and S 27.59%. Found C 30.98%, H 5.22%, N 36.19% and S 27.55%).

The second ligand was prepared by a method similar to that of the previous one by using 4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazide in place of thiosemicarbazide. (m.p. 231°, Requires C 56.25%, H 5.21%, N 21.88% and S 16.67%. Found C 56.23%, H 5.24%, N 21.86% and S 16.62%).

Cobalt(II) complexes :

$CoL_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $CoL_1 \cdot 2H_2O$: A solution of the ligand (0.001 mole) was prepared by refluxing with

about 100 ml ethanol. $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.001 mole) dissolved in 25 ml of the same solvent was added to it. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted between 6-7 by adding NH_4OH . It was then digested on water bath for half an hour when a deep brown precipitate settled down. It was cooled, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused $CaCl_2$.

$CoL(B)_2$ and $CoL_1(B)_2$ (where $B = pyridine, 2, 3$ and $4-picolines$) : $Co(py)_2Cl_2$, $Co(2-pic)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $Co(3-pic)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $Co(4-pic)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were prepared by the usual procedures. The ligands (0.001 mole) were taken into solution by refluxing with alcohol. To this solution the cobalt adducts (0.001 mole) were added and the resulting solutions were refluxed for 4 hours. On cooling they yielded brownish compounds. These were filtered, washed with ethanol until free from pyridine or picolines, kept in open air for an hour and finally dried over fused $CaCl_2$. For the complexes of the second ligand (L_1H_2) the residues were washed with petroleum ether in place of ethanol, as all of them are highly soluble in ethanol.

Nickel(II) complexes :

NiL and $NiL_1 \cdot H_2O$: These were prepared by a method exactly similar to those used in the preparation of Co(II) complexes using $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ in place of $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$. Both of them were obtained as granular brown solids.

$NiL(B)_2$ and $NiL_1(B)_2$ (where $B = py, 2-pic, 3-pic$ and $4-pic$) : $Ni(py)_2Cl_2$, $Ni(2-pic)_2Cl_2$, $Ni(3-pic)_2Cl_2$ and $Ni(4-pic)_2Cl_2$ were prepared by the usual procedures. The method of preparation of these adducts [$NiL(B)_2$ and $NiL_1(B)_2$] are identical to those of the corresponding Co(II) complexes.

Copper(II) complexes : **CuL :** Thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mole) was taken into solution by refluxing it with 200 ml of alcohol. To it biacetyl (0.001 mole) was added and the resulting solution was then refluxed for about an hour. Now,

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Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.001 mole) was added to it and refluxed for another hour and the pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 5-6 with NH₄OH. On cooling a deep-ash coloured compound separated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused CaCl₂.

CuL₁ : To an alcoholic solution of the ligand (0.001), Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O (0.001 mole) was added and refluxed for half an hour. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted between 5-6 by NH₄OH. On cooling, a brownish compound separated out. This was filtered, washed with ethanol and finally dried over fused CaCl₂.

CuL(B)₂ and CuL₁(B)₂ (where B=py, 2-pic, 3-pic and 4-pic) : The complexes were prepared by a method identical to those of NiL(B)₂ and NiL₁(B)₂ using Cu(py)₂Cl₂·2H₂O, Cu(2-pic)₂Cl₂·2H₂O, Cu(3-pic)₂Cl₂·2H₂O and Cu(4-pic)₂Cl₂·2H₂O in place of the corresponding nickel complexes. These were obtained as granular brownish solids.

Analyses : Carbon and hydrogen (for the ligands) were determined by microtechnique and nitrogen was estimated by semi-micro Dumas method. The

metals and sulphur were estimated by standard analytical procedures.

Physical measurements : Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured in a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were made with Pascal's constants⁷. The ir spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in the range 4000-250 cm⁻¹ with a Beckman IR 20A spectrophotometer using anhydrous KBr or CsBr as the matrix. Electronic absorption spectra of the insoluble complexes, in the visible region, were taken by the absorptions of dispersions of solid complexes as nujol mulls in a MOM-201 (Hungarian) spectrophotometer, using the technique of Lee *et al*⁸. The spectra of the soluble complexes were recorded in purified, bidistilled ethanol with a Shimadzu 210A UV-VIS spectrophotometer and a Cary 17D spectrophotometer. The absorption maxima of the complexes in the visible region (in cm⁻¹) are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

Solubility : The biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemi-carbazone complexes are more soluble in organic

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND SPECTRAL** (VISIBLE) DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF BIACETYL THIOSEMICARBAZONE (H₂L)

Complex	Analysis(%)*			μ_{eff} B.M. at 302°K	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
	Metal	Nitrogen	Sulfur		
CoL ₂ H ₂ O	18.05	25.78	19.61	4.7	22,222
	(18.15)	(25.85)	(19.69)		16,949
CoL(py) ₂	13.10	24.86	14.26	4.75	9,434
	(13.20)	(25.06)	(14.32)		21,739
CoL(2-pic) ₂	12.38	23.51	13.37	4.71	16,667
	(12.42)	(23.58)	(13.47)		9,217
CoL(3-pic) ₂	12.39	23.50	13.39	4.81	19,230
	(12.42)	(23.58)	(13.47)		16,667
CoL(4-pic) ₂	12.37	23.52	13.38	5.0	9,091
	(12.42)	(23.58)	(13.47)		20,833
NiL	20.30	23.99	22.10	Diamagnetic	16,129
	(20.34)	(23.99)	(22.17)		9,259
NiL(py) ₂	13.08	24.99	14.28	2.9	20,000
	(13.14)	(25.07)	(14.33)		9,259
NiL(2-pic) ₂	12.32	23.52	13.40	2.94	25,000
	(12.36)	(23.59)	(13.48)		16,393
NiL(3-pic) ₂	12.31	23.52	13.41	2.92	10,204
	(12.36)	(23.59)	(13.48)		16,898
NiL(4-pic) ₂	12.32	23.51	13.41	3.15	13,158
	(12.36)	(23.59)	(13.48)		10,204
CuL	21.60	28.58	21.79	1.67	16,667
	(21.64)	(28.62)	(21.81)		13,158
CuL(py) ₂	14.12	24.72	14.10	1.73	10,309
	(14.06)	(24.80)	(14.17)		17,241
CuL(2-pic) ₂	13.17	23.29	13.31	1.84	16,393
	(13.24)	(23.36)	(13.34)		16,667
CuL(3-pic) ₂	13.18	23.27	13.27	1.82	17,241
	(13.24)	(23.36)	(13.34)		16,667
CuL(4-pic) ₂	13.16	23.27	13.27	1.9	17,241
	(13.24)	(23.36)	(13.34)		16,667

** Spectra recorded in nujol mull.

* Values in the paranthesis represent the calculated values.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND SPECTRAL (VISIBLE) DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF BIACETYL-(4-PHENYL)-THIOSEMICARBAZONE (H_2L_1)

Complex	Analysis(%) ^a				μ_{eff} 303°K	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})	Ethanol ϵ_{max} (cm^{-1} mole ⁻¹)
	Metal	Nitrogen	Sulfur	Water			
CoL ₁ .2H ₂ O	12.33 (12.37)	17.56 (17.61)	13.38 (13.42)	7.49 (7.55)	4.72	19,231 ^a 9,009	54 7
CoL ₁ .(py) ₂	9.80 (9.85)	18.62 (18.70)	10.61 (10.68)	—	4.78	20,000 9,091	37 4
CoL ₁ .(2-pic) ₂	9.36 (9.41)	17.80 (17.86)	10.17 (10.21)	—	4.93	20,000 9,091	44 5
CoL ₁ .(3-pic) ₂	9.37 (9.41)	17.80 (17.86)	10.16 (10.21)	—	4.82	18,519 9,091	46 5
CoL ₁ .(4-pic) ₂	9.36 (9.41)	17.78 (17.86)	10.18 (10.21)	—	5.0	18,519 9,091	45 6
NiL ₁ .H ₂ O	12.78 (12.80)	18.29 (18.31)	13.92 (13.95)	3.89 (3.92)	Diamagnetic	25,000 ^b	—
NiL ₁ .(py) ₂	9.79 (9.81)	18.69 (18.71)	10.64 (10.70)	—	2.97	16,667 13,158 10,204	10.74 7.6 11.14
NiL ₁ .(2-pic) ₂	9.33 (9.37)	17.82 (17.87)	10.15 (10.21)	—	2.98	16,873 13,500 10,101	10.0 14.7 14.9
NiL ₁ .(3-pic) ₂	9.32 (9.37)	17.84 (17.87)	10.17 (10.21)	—	3.01	15,625 10,204	11.14 15.17
NiL ₁ .(4-pic) ₂	9.32 (9.37)	17.84 (17.87)	10.17 (10.21)	—	3.14	16,393 10,204	10.19 16.17
CuL ₁	14.25 (14.26)	18.84 (18.85)	14.34 (14.36)	—	1.6	16,129 ^c	86.15
CuL ₁ .(py) ₂	10.60 (10.53)	18.50 (18.56)	10.51 (10.60)	—	1.74	16,949	50.17
CuL ₁ .(2-pic) ₂	10.12 (10.06)	17.70 (17.73)	10.23 (10.13)	—	1.72	16,393	40.37
CuL ₁ .(3-pic) ₂	10.10 (10.06)	17.67 (17.73)	10.02 (10.13)	—	1.81	16,529	42.63
CuL ₁ .(4-pic) ₂	9.98 (10.06)	17.68 (17.73)	10.04 (10.13)	—	1.79	16,949	39.40

^a Values in the parenthesis represent the calculated values.
^a=methanol, b=nujol, c=nitromethane.

solvents than the corresponding biacetyl thiosemi-carbazone complexes probably due to the presence of the phenyl rings in the former.

Magnetic moment values: The magnetic moments of the Co(II) complexes under investigation lie in the range of 4.70–5.00 B.M., which are higher than the spin only value of three unpaired electrons and are considered to be due to large orbital contribution in a distorted octahedral environment. The nickel(II) complexes (NiL and NiL₁.H₂O) under study are diamagnetic in nature indicating that they are of the square-planar configuration. The magnetic moment of all the adducts of these two parent complexes of Ni(II) are within the range of 2.9–3.15 B.M. This observation indicates some orbital contribution, as the spin-only value of a 'two unpaired electron system' should be 2.83 B.M. The magnetic moment values of all the Cu(II) complexes being studied lie within the range of 1.67 to 1.90 B.M.

Visible spectra: The spectra of the Co(II) complexes (studied here) in solution exhibit two broad bands; one in the region of 9,500 cm^{-1} and the other in the region of 20,000 cm^{-1} [Tables 1 and 2]. The bands near 20,000 cm^{-1} correspond to the ν_3 band due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition in an octahedral field and the band at 9,500 cm^{-1} are due

to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1 band) transition in an octahedral environment⁹. In all these cases, no visible splitting of either ν_1 or ν_3 bands is observed, which may be due to superimposition of the closely spaced components leading to a broad nature of the bands. The ν_2 band is not observed in these cases, since this particular transition is a two-electron process and consequently the intensity of this band may be too low to be detected^{10,11}. The mull spectra of the Co(II) complexes, except CoL(4-pic)₂, however consists of three bands corresponding to the three transitions indicative of an octahedral environment, and this is in accord with their magnetic moment values. The band near 17,000 cm^{-1} may be the ν_2 band which arises out of ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ transition in an octahedral field⁹. For the diamagnetic nickel(II) complex, no band in the visible region is observed excepting for the intense band around 25,000 cm^{-1} . For the square-planar Ni(II) compounds, the band arising from ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transition usually occurs at about 20,000 cm^{-1} and the shifting of this band to a much higher energy region, may be due to the coupling of the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ band with the charge transfer band¹². The intense brown colour of the complexes is probably due to the presence of such a charge transfer band. The visible spectra of all paramagnetic Ni(II) complexes included in the present

study [Tables 1 and 2] show mainly two broad band and no clear splitting of either ν_1 or ν_2 band is observed. The nature of the bands suggests the presence of other closely spaced bands which are probably masked by the main band. The broad ν_2 band appears in the region 15,625–16,667 cm^{-1} . In several cases, there appears a band of weak intensity in the region of 12,500–13,333 cm^{-1} which, according to Jørgensen¹³, may be due to the spin-orbit coupling between $^1E_g(D)$ and $^3T_{1g}(F)$ state of the Ni(II) ion. Such bands are also observed in some of the Ni(II) complexes of the type $\text{NiL}(\text{B})_2$ and $\text{NiL}_1(\text{B})_2$ [vide Tables 1 and 2]. These complexes also exhibit one broad band in the region of 10,101–10,309 cm^{-1} due to transition $^3A_g(F) \rightarrow ^3T_2(F)$ (ν_1). The visible spectra of all the Cu(II) complexes under investigation exhibit a composite broad band around 16,529–17,241 cm^{-1} and it is very difficult to make precise assignment of this band^{12a}.

Infrared spectra: The highest frequency band of the ligand biacetyl thiosemicarbazone (LH_2) at 3400 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the asymmetric stretching vibration of the terminal- NH_2 group. The other bands at 3240 cm^{-1} , 3180 cm^{-1} and 3140 cm^{-1} may be due to the superimposed form of the symmetric $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ bands of the amino and the imino groups. It is almost impossible to identify separately the components $\nu(\text{NH})$ and $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ owing to their overlapping nature. But, in the case of the second ligand, biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemicarbazone (L_1H_2) the two highest frequency bands are observed at 3320 cm^{-1} and 3280 cm^{-1} which are possibly due to the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ of the two different $-\text{NH}$ moiety present. A doublet is located around 1600 cm^{-1} for the first ligand which is probably due to the partial overlapping of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$. But this doublet is absent in the spectrum of the second ligand as there is no terminal $-\text{NH}_2$ group in it and only a single band at 1590 cm^{-1} is observed. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (imine) stretching vibration occurs near 1590 cm^{-1} in both the ligands¹⁴. The band near 825 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations¹⁵.

The band around 3400 cm^{-1} of biacetyl thiosemicarbazone is not affected during chelation, which indicates that the terminal $-\text{NH}_2$ does not take part in coordination. Moreover in the ir spectra of some of the complexes a number of sharp bands are observed in this region, which may be due to $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu(\text{OH})$. In some complexes a broad band around 3400–3100 cm^{-1} arising out of the stretching vibrations of coordinated or lattice water molecules mixed with $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu_{as}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ is observed.

In the case of the biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemicarbazone, most of the complexes exhibit a broad band around 3300–3050 cm^{-1} , arising out of the $\nu_{(\text{O}-\text{H})}$ of coordinated or lattice-water mixed with $\nu(\text{NH})$.

In the case of the metal complexes of biacetyl thiosemicarbazone the most interesting feature noted is that, the doublet, observed in the ir spectrum of the ligand near 1600 cm^{-1} , splits into two

components. The higher one goes up to 1620 cm^{-1} and is probably due to the bending mode of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group which remains practically unaffected in the complexes and shows that the $-\text{NH}_2$ moiety does not take part in coordination. The other component, which is due to the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ (imine) stretch, suffers a reduction of 5–15 cm^{-1} . This indicates the involvements of the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ (imine) group in coordination. In the case of biacetyl-(4-phenyl)-thiosemicarbazone, the band around 1600 cm^{-1} suffers a reduction of 5–15 cm^{-1} indicating that bonding occurs through the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ (imine) group. In the case of the metal complexes of both the ligands, the band around 830 cm^{-1} (due to $\nu > \text{C}=\text{S}$) is absent. From this observation it may be concluded that in these complexes enolisation of the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group takes place.

From a detailed analysis of the far ir spectra of the metal pyridine complexes, Clark *et al.*¹⁶ concluded that both the in plane and out of plane pyridine ring deformation vibrations, occurring at 604 and 405 cm^{-1} suffers a positive shift by 20–75 cm^{-1} on coordination to a metal ion. As an indication of pyridine coordination in the pyridinated Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes a band around 670 cm^{-1} has been noticed which may be due to in-plane deformation vibration of the pyridine ring. In several cases of metal complexes involving pyridine, a fairly strong band around 460 cm^{-1} is assigned to the out of plane deformation of the pyridine ring vibration and is taken as an indication of coordination of the pyridine molecule to the metal ion.

In several of our complexes involving 2-picoline, 3-picoline or 4-picoline the bands around 670 cm^{-1} and 465 cm^{-1} have been noticed and may be assigned to the in plane deformation vibration and out of the plane deformation of the substituted pyridine ring. This may be taken as an indication of coordination of the picoline molecules to the metal ions.

The band around 480 cm^{-1} is assigned to the metal nitrogen stretching vibration¹⁷ and the band around 340 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu_{(\text{M}-\text{S})}$ ¹⁸ as both of these bands are absent in the ir spectra of the ligands and are slightly shifted with the change of the metal ion.

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References

1. N. N. ORLOVA, V. A. AKSENOVA, D. A. SCLIDOVKIN, N. S. BOGDANOVA and G. N. PERSKHIN, *Russ. Pharm. Toxic.*, 1968, 348.
2. C. W. JOHNSON, J. W. JOYNER and R. P. PERRY, *Antibiotics and Chemotherapy*, 1952, 2, 636.
3. D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, 203 and the references cited therein.
4. B. L. FRIEDLANDER and F. A. FRENCH, *Cancer Res.*, 1958, 18, 1286, 1290.
5. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, *Cancer Res.*, 1965, 25, 1454.

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6. F. A. FRENCH and E. J. BLANZ, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 585.
7. P. W. SELWOOD, 'Magneto Chemistry', Interscience Publishers, New York, 1956, 92.
8. R. H. LEE, E. GRISWOLD and J. KLEINBERG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1278.
9. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier Publishing Company, 1968, 320.
10. C. K. JÖRGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 1502.
11. S. KOIDE, *Phil. Mag.*, 1959, **4**, 243.
12. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier Publishing Company, 1968, 343.
- 12a. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy', Elsevier Publishing Company, 1968, 357.
13. C. K. JÖRGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 1362.
14. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The infrared spectra of complex molecules', Chapman and Hall, London, 1975, 227.
15. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The infrared spectra of complex molecules', Chapman and Hall, London, 1975, 401.
16. R. J. H. CLARK and C. S. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 350.
17. R. A. CONDRADE and K. J. NAKAMOTO, *Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 2590.
18. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", A Wiley—Interscience Publication, 1978, 335.